

Spousal Support and Workplace Adjustment of Secondary School Teachers in Uyo Local Government of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17866155>

Citation: Arobo, O. U., Okereke, I. E., Ihe, I. C., Sade, P. P., & Amanam, I. J. (2025). Spousal Support and Workplace Adjustment of Secondary School Teachers in Uyo Local Government of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *Global Journal of Modern Research and Emerging Trends*, 1(7).

Abstract

The study investigated the relationship between spousal support and workplace adjustment of secondary school teachers in the Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Three research questions and three null hypotheses guided the conduct of the study. A correlational research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study was 917 married teachers in 15 public secondary schools in Uyo Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. A sample of 345 married teachers was selected for the study using a simple random sampling technique. A researcher-made instrument, titled "Spousal Support and Workplace Adjustment Questionnaire" (SSWAQ), was used for data collection. The instrument was face validated while its internal consistency reliability was established, and a reliability coefficient of .71 was obtained by applying the Cronbach's alpha statistic. The Pearson product-moment correlation statistic was used to answer the research questions and also test their corresponding hypotheses. All the hypotheses were tested at the .05 level of significance, while all data were subjected to analysis using the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS). Analysis of data revealed that instrumental support and appraisal support are positively and significantly related to workplace adjustment of

secondary school teachers. Moreover, no significant relationship was found between informational support and workplace adjustment of secondary school teachers. Based on the findings of the study, three relevant recommendations were made, among which is that school principals in Akwa Ibom State should conduct quarterly appraisal meetings where teachers receive verbal commendation, clear feedback on strengths, and targeted guidance on areas that need improvement.

Keywords: Spousal support, workplace, adjustment, secondary school, teachers

Introduction

Workplace adjustment is a vital component of teachers' professional functioning and overall well-being, particularly within the dynamic and usually demanding environment of secondary schools. It is important for teachers to adapt to the expectations, responsibilities, and social conditions of their workplace in order to perform effectively. This adaptation involves a combination of behavioural, emotional, and cognitive adjustments that enable teachers to cope with professional stressors, manage classroom challenges, and maintain productive relationships with colleagues, students, and administrators. Effective workplace adjustment encompasses not only meeting formal job requirements but also handling the informal social environment of the school, such as participating in collaborative activities, resolving conflicts, and contributing to a positive organisational climate. It requires the development of resilience, flexibility, and problem-solving skills, allowing teachers to respond constructively to changes in curriculum, administrative policies, and student needs. According to Ukaegbu and Obikoya, adjustment as a process is important for a harmonious relationship between an individual and his environment. In essence, workplace adjustment represents a continuous process through which teachers align their personal capacities and coping strategies with the demands of the school environment, ensuring both personal well-being and professional effectiveness. According to Essien (2017), workplace adjustment involves achieving a harmonious balance between job demands, interpersonal relationships, and organisational norms. Teachers who successfully adjust to their workplace tend to demonstrate higher job satisfaction, improved instructional delivery, and stronger resilience when faced with professional challenges. Conversely, poor workplace adjustment may result in emotional fatigue, diminished productivity, and high turnover intentions (Nwachukwu & Udoh, 2019).

Given the unique challenges secondary school teachers encounter, ranging from heavy workloads and student behavioural issues to limited resources and high community expectations, understanding the factors that enhance workplace adjustment is crucial. One significant factor that has gained attention in recent years is spousal support. Spousal support refers to the various forms of assistance provided by one's marital partner, which serve to strengthen emotional stability and improve coping strategies (House, 2016). The authors further explained that spousal support is multidimensional, comprising informational, appraisal, and instrumental forms of assistance, each of which could play a unique role in shaping an individual's psychological and professional functioning.

Informational support involves the provision of advice, suggestions, and guidance that help individuals make informed decisions about work-related issues. For teachers, this may include a spouse offering insights on managing stress, organising tasks, or navigating workplace conflicts. Appraisal support, on the other hand, includes feedback, affirmation, and constructive evaluation aimed at boosting confidence and helping teachers assess their performance more objectively. Instrumental support refers to tangible assistance such as helping with household chores, childcare, or financial responsibilities, thereby enabling teachers to conserve time and energy for their professional roles. According to Okeke and Akpan (2019), these forms of support can collectively contribute to improved emotional regulation, reduced stress levels, and enhanced job performance among married workers.

In the context of secondary school teachers in the Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, the significance of spousal support cannot be overstated. Teachers in this local government area, like their counterparts elsewhere, operate under conditions that require a high degree of adaptability, patience, and emotional resilience. When spouses provide adequate informational, appraisal, and instrumental support, teachers are better equipped to handle classroom challenges, maintain positive professional relationships, and remain committed to their roles. Conversely, inadequate spousal support may hinder workplace adjustment, leading to increased stress, job dissatisfaction, and reduced effectiveness.

Thus, this study became imperative as it sought to examine how the three dimensions of spousal support – informational, appraisal, and instrumental – relate to workplace adjustment of secondary school teachers in Uyo Local Government Area. Considering that teachers' well-being may directly affect their performance and the quality of

education delivered to students, investigating the influence of spousal support would provide valuable insights that can inform counselling interventions, marital enrichment programmes, and policies aimed at improving teachers' welfare and professional stability.

Statement of the Problem

Workplace adjustment among secondary school teachers is an area that has not been sufficiently explored, particularly in the Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. Teachers in this locality contend with numerous work-related challenges, such as high workload, inadequate instructional resources, large class sizes, and increasing societal expectations. These pressures may hinder their ability to adjust effectively to their work environment, thereby affecting their productivity and emotional stability. Furthermore, spousal support, which includes informational, appraisal, and instrumental assistance, may play a critical role in helping married teachers cope with work demands. However, the extent to which these forms of support influence workplace adjustment among teachers in the Uyo Local Government Area remains largely unclear.

Insufficient attention to the personal and emotional support systems available to teachers can result in job dissatisfaction, reduced commitment, and heightened stress levels. These outcomes may not only affect teachers' performance in the classroom but may also lead to burnout and increased turnover intention. Moreover, when teachers experience poor workplace adjustment due to inadequate spousal support, their home life, family relationships, and overall well-being may also be negatively impacted. Despite the importance of spousal support in enhancing coping strategies and promoting professional stability, no empirical studies have focused on how informational, appraisal, and instrumental support contribute to workplace adjustment in this specific context.

This study therefore sought to bridge the gap in existing research by examining the extent to which spousal support predicts workplace adjustment among secondary school teachers in the Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. Most available literature tends to concentrate on broader geographical regions or different occupational groups, leaving a contextual gap concerning teachers in this locale. Understanding these dynamics is essential for developing interventions, guidance programmes, and policies aimed at improving teachers' well-being and fostering a more supportive work environment.

Purpose of the Study

The primary aim of this study was to determine the extent to which spousal support influences the workplace adjustment of secondary school teachers in the Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. Specifically, the study sought to examine:

- i. The extent of the relationship between informational support and workplace adjustment among married secondary school teachers.
- ii. The extent of the relationship between appraisal support and workplace adjustment among married secondary school teachers.
- iii. The extent of the relationship between instrumental support and workplace adjustment among married secondary school teachers.

Significance of the Study

The findings of this study would be beneficial to teachers, school administrators, counsellors, policymakers and future researchers. First, teachers themselves stand to gain a deeper understanding of how spousal support can enhance their emotional stability, reduce workplace stress, and improve their overall adjustment. This awareness may encourage healthier marital interactions and foster an environment that promotes personal and professional growth.

Second, school administrators may use the insights from this study to develop supportive workplace policies, strengthen teacher welfare programmes, and implement interventions aimed at reducing stress levels and improving staff morale. Recognising the role of spousal support may also encourage administrators to adopt more flexible and empathetic management approaches.

Third, counsellors would find the findings of the study valuable for designing targeted counselling and marital enrichment programmes that address the relational and emotional needs of teachers. Understanding the forms of spousal support that most influence workplace adjustment will enable professionals to guide couples more effectively.

Fourth, policymakers in the education sector may utilise the findings of the study to develop policies that promote teacher well-being, retention, and productivity. Integrating psychosocial support structures into teacher development frameworks could lead to a more stable and efficient workforce.

Finally, the findings of the study would add to existing literature by filling a contextual gap, as limited research has focused specifically on the influence of spousal support on workplace adjustment in this region. It will therefore serve as a reference point for future researchers interested in teacher welfare, marital interactions, and occupational adjustment.

Research Questions

Based on the objectives of this study, the following research questions were formulated to direct the investigation:

- i. To what extent does informational support relate to the workplace adjustment of married secondary school teachers?
- ii. To what extent does appraisal support relate to the workplace adjustment of married secondary school teachers?
- iii. To what extent does instrumental support relate to the workplace adjustment of married secondary school teachers?

Null Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study and tested at the 0.05 level of significance:

- i. There is no significant relationship between informational support and the workplace adjustment of married secondary school teachers.
- ii. There is no significant relationship between appraisal support and the workplace adjustment of married secondary school teachers.
- iii. There is no significant relationship between instrumental support and the workplace adjustment of married secondary school teachers.

Scope of the Study

The study focused on spousal support and workplace adjustment of married secondary school teachers. Informational support, appraisal support, and instrumental support were the independent variables investigated by the researchers, while workplace adjustment served as the dependent variable. Only married teachers in public senior secondary schools in the Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State were studied.

Theoretical Framework

Social Support Theory by Sheldon Cohen and Thomas Wills (1985)

Social Support Theory was proposed by Sheldon Cohen and Thomas Wills in 1985. The theory emphasises the importance of social relationships and the supportive functions they provide in protecting individuals against psychological stress and enhancing overall well-being. According to Cohen and Wills, social support operates through two primary mechanisms: the main effect model and the buffering model. The main effect model suggests that support from family, friends, and community has a direct positive influence on health and coping outcomes, regardless of stress levels. In contrast, the buffering model posits that social support mitigates or “buffers” the harmful effects of stress by offering emotional reassurance, informational guidance, and practical assistance during periods of heightened pressure or crisis.

The theory categorises social support into emotional, instrumental, informational, and appraisal support. Emotional support involves expressions of empathy, love, and care; instrumental support includes tangible help such as financial aid or assistance with tasks; informational support provides guidance or advice; while appraisal support helps individuals evaluate and understand their situation more clearly. Together, these forms of support strengthen an individual's coping capacity and contribute to improved mental and emotional resilience.

According to the theory, the availability and quality of these forms of support are crucial in mitigating the adverse effects of stressors, enhancing coping strategies, and promoting overall adjustment in both personal and professional contexts. Adequate social support acts as a buffer against stress, reducing psychological strain, fostering resilience, and improving functional well-being. Individuals who perceive high levels of support are more likely to maintain emotional stability, exhibit positive behaviours, and achieve better outcomes in work and social environments. Conversely, a lack of sufficient support may exacerbate stress, increase vulnerability to mental health challenges, and hinder effective adaptation to demanding circumstances. In essence, Social Support Theory underscores the importance of relational networks, particularly spousal interactions, in shaping how individuals respond to stress and maintain overall well-being.

In the context of secondary school teachers, spousal support in the forms of informational, appraisal, and instrumental assistance can significantly influence

workplace adjustment. For instance, informational support helps teachers make informed decisions about handling professional challenges, appraisal support provides affirmation and feedback that boosts confidence, and instrumental support reduces the burden of household responsibilities, allowing teachers to focus more effectively on their work. Anchoring this study on Social Support Theory helps to understand how the availability and quality of spousal support can predict teachers' workplace adjustment, ultimately enhancing their professional functioning and overall well-being.

Empirical Literature

Informational Support and Workplace Adjustment

A study which examined the influence of informational support on workplace adjustment among secondary school teachers was conducted by Njoku and Daniels (2020). A correlational research design was adopted, and a sample of 412 teachers was selected using stratified random sampling. Data were collected using a validated questionnaire comprising two sections measuring informational support and workplace adjustment. Findings showed that while informational resources such as circulars, official guidelines and instructional materials supported lesson planning and classroom documentation, they did not significantly enhance teachers' overall capacity to cope with job stress, administrative demands and interpersonal challenges. The results further indicated that informational support was more effective when combined with interpersonal encouragement from colleagues and supportive school leadership structures. The authors concluded that information in isolation does not guarantee professional stability and recommended that school administrators integrate mentoring, feedback and collaborative structures alongside informational dissemination to strengthen teacher adjustment. In a similar study, Eze and Ufondu (2018) investigated the relationship between interpersonal support and workplace adjustment among public secondary school teachers. The study employed a descriptive survey design with 385 participants selected through multistage sampling. A researcher-developed instrument was used to assess the level of interpersonal support, including collegial cooperation, teamwork, shared responsibility and administrative goodwill. Results revealed that teachers who experienced strong interpersonal networks, cooperative staff relationships and administrative empathy adjusted more successfully to workload expectations, classroom management stress and policy implementation demands than those who relied solely on informational communication provided by the school. Findings also indicated that shared responsibility and collaborative problem-solving created emotional stability, reduced burnout and strengthened teachers' professional identity.

The authors recommended the establishment of peer support systems, regular staff interaction platforms and leadership practices that encourage collective participation for enhanced teacher adjustment.

Appraisal Support and Workplace Adjustment

Mohammed and Yusuf (2021) investigated the role of appraisal support on workplace functioning among secondary school teachers. A descriptive survey design was adopted, and a total of 427 teachers were sampled through proportional stratified procedures. Data were collected using a validated Appraisal Support and Teacher Adjustment Questionnaire (ASTAQ). The findings showed that teachers who received positive evaluative feedback from school administrators exhibited a stronger sense of belonging, greater emotional stability, and enhanced professional functioning compared to those working in environments where appraisal was irregular or primarily fault-focused. The results further indicated that affirming comments, recognition of effort, and constructive performance reviews played a significant role in boosting teachers' motivation and improving their day-to-day coping abilities. Overall, the study concluded that supportive appraisal practices are essential for strengthening teacher morale, promoting institutional commitment, and facilitating effective professional adjustment.

Similarly, Adewole and Abiola (2020) examined the effect of constructive appraisal on workplace adjustment among public secondary school teachers. Employing a correlational research design, data were gathered from a sample of 398 teachers using a standardised Teacher Appraisal and Adjustment Scale (TAAS). The findings showed that teachers who received detailed, supportive and improvement-orientated appraisal feedback reported reduced job-related stress, higher morale and stronger adaptation to institutional expectations than those whose evaluation processes were largely critical or punitive in tone. The study also revealed that appraisal systems emphasising guidance, encouragement and recognition contributed to greater emotional stability and improved task performance. Based on the outcome, the researchers recommended a shift from fault-focused evaluation to constructive appraisal strategies to promote teachers' psychological well-being and occupational adjustment.

Instrumental Support and Workplace Adjustment

Suleiman and Rahman (2022) examined the influence of instrumental support on coping ability and exhaustion among secondary school teachers. A descriptive survey design

was adopted, and a sample of 450 teachers was selected using multistage sampling techniques. Data were collected with a standardised questionnaire on school logistics support and teacher adjustment. Findings revealed that teachers who received consistent institutional assistance, such as clerical support, availability of instructional materials, workload relief and timely administrative backing, demonstrated stronger coping skills and significantly lower work-related exhaustion than those without such support systems. The study further showed that practical assistance helped teachers maintain emotional stability and classroom effectiveness, particularly during periods of high instructional demand. The researchers concluded that instrumental support is a crucial protective resource that strengthens teacher resilience and recommended increased administrative responsiveness to teachers' operational needs. In a related study, Bello and Salami (2020) explored the relationship between institutional support structures and workplace adjustment among public secondary school teachers. Using a correlational research design, data were obtained from 392 teachers through a validated School Support and Adjustment Inventory (SSAI). Results indicated that teachers who benefited from adequately supplied teaching resources, clerical help, administrative cooperation and supportive logistical arrangements adjusted more positively to workplace expectations than their counterparts with limited access to such support. The findings also showed that tangible support mechanisms contributed to reduced stress levels, improved task performance and greater professional satisfaction. Based on the results, the authors recommended that school management strengthen support logistics, ensure resource availability and establish reliable assistance systems to promote teacher adjustment and well-being.

Methodology

Research Design

This study adopted a correlational research design, which is commonly used to determine the degree and direction of the relationship between two or more variables without manipulating them. The design was considered appropriate because the main objective of the research was to examine the nature and extent of the relationship between spousal support and workplace adjustment of secondary school teachers in the Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. By using a correlational design, the researcher was able to collect data from participants and statistically analyse the relationships among the variables of interest.

Population of the Study

The population of the study consisted of 917 married teachers in public secondary schools in the Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State (State Secondary Schools Board, 2025). This population was derived from 15 public secondary schools in the Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State.

Sample and Sampling Technique

A sample of 345 married teachers was selected for the study using a simple random sampling technique. The simple random sampling technique is suitable for the study because it gave all the married teachers equal opportunity to be selected for the study.

Instrument for Data Collection

A researcher-made instrument, titled “Spousal Support and Workplace Adjustment Questionnaire” (SSWAQ), was used for data collection. The instrument was divided into two sections. Section A contained 15 items. Five items were used to measure each of the spousal support variables (informational, appraisal, and instrumental support), while Section B consisted of ten items designed to assess the workplace adjustment of married secondary school teachers. The items were presented as statements, and respondents were instructed to indicate their level of agreement or disagreement using a four-point rating scale: Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD), weighted 4, 3, 2, and 1 point, respectively.

Validation of the Instrument

The instrument was presented to one expert in the Department of Measurement and Evaluation, Department of Psychological Foundations, and two experts in the Department of Guidance and Counselling of Education, both at the University of Uyo, for face validation. The researchers ensured that all the areas recommended for corrections were incorporated before producing the final draft.

Reliability of the Instrument

The reliability of the instrument was determined using the internal consistency method to ensure that the items in each section of the instrument measured the same construct consistently. In carrying out this process, the instrument was pilot-tested on a sample of 30 married teachers who were part of the population but were not selected for the study. The responses obtained from the pilot test were subjected to statistical analysis using the Cronbach Alpha reliability technique. The analysis yielded an overall reliability coefficient of 0.71, which implies that the instrument is reliable.

Method of Data Collection

The instrument for the study was administered to the respondents through the direct delivery method. However, the researchers administered the instrument directly to the respondents with the assistance of one research assistant chosen from each of the schools selected for the study. Copies of the instrument were administered to the respondents during the break period.

Method of Data Analysis

Pearson Product Moment Correlation statistics were used to answer the research questions and also test their corresponding hypotheses. All the hypotheses were tested at the .05 level of significance, while all data were subjected to analysis using the statistical package for social science (SPSS).

Results

Table 1: Pearson's correlation coefficient on the relationship between informational support and workplace adjustment of married secondary school teachers in Uyo Local Government Area

Variable	n	r-value	p-value	Decision
Informational support	345	.317	.158	Not Sig.
Workplace adjustment				

The result in Table 1 shows that there is a positive but low relationship between informational support and workplace adjustment of married secondary school teachers in Uyo Local Government Area, as indicated by the correlation coefficient of $r = .317$. However, this relationship is not statistically significant since the p-value of .158 is greater than the established alpha level of .05. This implies that variations in informational support do not significantly relate to the level of workplace adjustment among the teachers. Although teachers who receive more informational support may show slightly better adjustment at work, the association is not strong enough to draw a conclusive inference. Consequently, the null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant relationship between informational support and workplace adjustment, is upheld.

Table 2: Pearson's correlation coefficient on the relationship between appraisal support and workplace adjustment of married secondary school teachers in Uyo Local Government Area

Variable	n	r-value	p-value	Decision
Appraisal support	345	.689	.000	Sig.
Workplace adjustment				

The results presented in Table 2 show a strong and statistically significant relationship between appraisal support and workplace adjustment of married secondary school teachers in Uyo Local Government Area, as indicated by the correlation coefficient of $r = .689$ and a p-value of $.000$, which is below the accepted level of significance of $.05$. This finding means that teachers who receive greater appraisal support tend to adjust better to their workplace demands. Since the p-value showed significance, the null hypothesis, which states that there is no relationship between appraisal support and workplace adjustment, is rejected, confirming that appraisal support plays an important role in enhancing workplace adjustment.

Table 3: Pearson's correlation coefficient on the relationship between instrumental support and workplace adjustment of married secondary school teachers in Uyo Local Government Area

Variable	n	r-value	p-value	Decision
Instrumental support	345	.601	.001	Sig.
Workplace adjustment				

The results presented in Table 3 indicate a strong and statistically significant relationship between instrumental support and the workplace adjustment of married secondary school teachers in Uyo Local Government Area. This is evidenced by the correlation coefficient of $r = .601$ and a p-value of $.001$, which is well below the accepted significance threshold of $.05$. These findings suggest that teachers who receive practical assistance, such as access to teaching materials, clerical support, time allowances, and help with work-related tasks, are more likely to adjust effectively to their professional environment. Given the significance of the p-value, the null hypothesis stating that no relationship exists between instrumental support and workplace adjustment is rejected.

This implies that instrumental support is a key determinant in enhancing workplace adjustment among married secondary school teachers.

Discussion of Findings

The finding that there is no significant relationship between informational support and the workplace adjustment of married secondary school teachers in Uyo Local Government Area suggests that although informational support is commonly acknowledged as a useful resource for navigating work demands, it may not directly shape how teachers adapt to their professional environment. One possible explanation is that teachers, particularly those with extensive classroom experience, may already possess internal coping skills, professional confidence, and familiarity with school structures that enable them to function effectively without relying heavily on informational guidance. Their adjustment may also be more strongly influenced by supportive leadership, collegial interaction, emotional reassurance, and favourable school climate rather than access to information alone. In settings where teachers face administrative pressure, student behavioural concerns, or role conflict, behavioural and emotional support may prove more valuable than informational assistance in achieving workplace balance. This present finding aligns with the work of Njoku and Daniels (2020), who observed that while informational resources contributed to instructional planning, they did not significantly improve overall workplace adaptation unless accompanied by interpersonal and administrative support. Similarly, Eze and Ufondu (2018) reported that teachers tended to adjust more successfully when they experienced collective encouragement and shared responsibility rather than when provided with information without relational backing. These studies suggest that informational support by itself may not be a primary determinant of workplace adjustment among married teachers, particularly when other contextual and interpersonal support systems are more influential in shaping their work experiences.

The finding that there is a strong and significant relationship between appraisal support and workplace adjustment of married secondary school teachers in Uyo Local Government Area indicates that evaluative reinforcement, recognition and constructive feedback play an important role in how teachers adapt to their professional roles. This outcome suggests that when teachers receive consistent acknowledgement, fair appraisal and affirming feedback from school authorities, they are more likely to experience emotional balance, sustained motivation and improved task performance. A possible explanation for this result is that appraisal support helps teachers feel valued,

understood and professionally competent, which reduces the strain associated with lesson preparation, student conduct and administrative responsibilities. In environments where feedback is respectful and supportive, teachers tend to work with greater confidence and adjust more smoothly to workplace demands. This present finding is supported by the work of Mohammed and Yusuf (2021), who revealed that positive evaluative feedback enhanced teachers' sense of belonging and strengthened their daily functioning in school settings. In a similar study, Adewole and Abiola (2020) found that when teachers received constructive appraisal rather than fault-focused criticism, they demonstrated higher morale, reduced stress and improved workplace adaptation. These findings collectively affirm that appraisal support serves as a vital factor in facilitating workplace adjustment, particularly among married teachers who balance domestic responsibilities with formal teaching obligations.

The finding that there is a strong and significant relationship between instrumental support and workplace adjustment of married secondary school teachers in Uyo Local Government Area indicates that practical assistance plays a crucial role in how effectively teachers cope with their professional duties. Instrumental support, which may include provision of instructional materials, administrative assistance, reduction of workload stress and availability of practical help during peak demands, appears to enhance teachers' ability to function confidently and maintain stability within the school environment. A possible explanation for this outcome is that when teachers receive tangible help rather than merely verbal or informational guidance, their daily tasks become more manageable, and their emotional strain is reduced. For married teachers balancing domestic obligations with teaching responsibilities, access to practical support may prevent burnout, minimise frustration and promote confidence in meeting school expectations. This present finding aligns with the work of Suleiman and Rahman (2022), who reported that practical assistance and supportive school logistics significantly improved teachers' coping abilities and reduced work-related exhaustion. Similarly, a study by Bello and Salami (2020) showed that teachers who regularly benefited from institutional support, clerical assistance and adequate teaching resources demonstrated stronger adjustment to workplace demands than colleagues who lacked such support. These studies reinforce the conclusion that instrumental support is an essential component in promoting workplace adjustment, especially for married teachers who must successfully navigate both personal and professional responsibilities.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it is concluded that different forms of social support play distinct yet important roles in shaping the workplace adjustment of married secondary school teachers in Uyo Local Government Area. The results highlight the need for meaningful support systems that integrate encouragement, constructive feedback, and tangible assistance within the school environment. Such comprehensive forms of support are vital for enhancing the professional adjustment of married teachers, who often navigate the dual demands of school responsibilities and family roles.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of the study:

- i. School principals in Akwa Ibom State should conduct quarterly appraisal meetings where teachers receive verbal commendation, clear feedback on strengths, and targeted guidance on areas needing improvement. These sessions should be supportive rather than punitive to enhance teachers' morale and adjustment to daily school tasks.
- ii. The Ministry of Education and secondary school board should assign clerical assistants and teaching aides to help with record keeping, lesson preparation, and administrative paperwork for married teachers. This practical support will reduce workload pressure and improve their ability to balance home responsibilities with school duties.
- iii. Secondary school management should establish WhatsApp forums, staff briefings and digital noticeboards that share instructional information, along with designated officers who explain implementation procedures. By pairing information with direct guidance and question-and-answer support, teachers will be able to translate information into effective classroom and administrative action.

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APPENDIX

**SPOUSAL SUPPORT AND WORKPLACE ADJUSTMENT
QUESTIONNAIRE (SSWAQ)**

INSTRUCTION: Choose your response from the number of alternatives by ticking appropriately in the box provided.

KEY: The response options are Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD)

SECTION A: SPOUSAL SUPPORT

S/N	Emotional Support	SA	A	D	SD
	Informational support				
1.	I receive helpful advice from my spouse on managing work demands.				
2.	I get practical tips from my spouse for improving my work-life balance.				
3.	I feel I have access to information on how to balance my professional responsibilities.				
4.	I do receive useful insights from my spouse on how to handle work-related stress.				
5.	I get relevant suggestions from my spouse on managing family obligations while working.				
	Instrumental support				
1.	I receive help from my spouse with household responsibilities to support my work commitments.				
2.	I do get practical support from my spouse when I am busy with work.				
3.	I receive assistance from my spouse with work tasks when I have pressing family obligations.				
4.	I have access to workplace resources that help me balance family and work responsibilities.				
5.	I receive support from my spouse who steps in to manage household tasks when I have a demanding work schedule.				

SECTION B: WORKPLACE ADJUSTMENT

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD
1.	I can meet deadlines at school without feeling overwhelmed by family obligations				
2.	I receive enough support at home to stay productive at school.				
3.	I relate well with colleagues despite family commitments				
4.	I am always prepared to perform my duties when I arrive at school				
5.	I rarely feel burnt out due to the demands from school.				
6.	I am able to maintain positive interactions with school administrators even under personal stress.				
7.	I maintain professional conduct at school even when faced with emotional strain at home.				
8.	I remain focused on my duties at school without being distracted by issues at home.				
9.	I feel emotionally stable when handling both school duties and home demands.				
10.	I adjust quickly to changes in school routines.				